

INDIGENOUS PEOPLES AND INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

John Renshaw, May 2024

Themes

- Indigenous peoples have a vital role in ensuring that natural habitats (forests, rivers, wetlands) can be protected in order to slow current trends of climate change. This is important for everyone...
- In practice, many indigenous peoples are suffering major impacts from environmental degradation and climate change
- There is a very wide gap between the way international agencies view indigenous peoples and the reality on the ground. How to engage in a meaningful, effective way?
- Cases from Paraguay, Argentina and Brazil

DIVERSITY OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLES

Paraguay, Brazil and Argentina

- Violence and occupation of indigenous lands. Guarani communities in Amambay, Paraguay and in MS, Brazil. Expansion of ranching, soy and illicit crops
- Population growth and impact on settlement patterns
- Migration to urban areas. Argentina, Paraguay

Evolución de la población indígena, 1981 a 2022

En el siguiente gráfico puede apreciarse un crecimiento continuo, dado por el crecimiento natural, como también asociado al mejoramiento de la metodología de recolección.

INDIGENOUS PEOPLES OF ARGENTINA 2010 - (T=955,032)

PROVINCE	
Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires	52,872
Buenos Aires	252,733
Catamarca	5,778
Chaco	30,700
Chubut	36,557
Córdoba	43,091
Corrientes	4,228
Entre Ríos	11,227
Formosa	22,970
Jujuy	43,810
La Pampa	11,930
La Rioja	3,317
Mendoza	34,816
Misiones	9,282
Neuquén	36,578
Río Negro	38,874
Salta	59,866
San Juan	6,569
San Luis	6,537
Santa Cruz	7,956
Santa Fe	40,067
Santiago del Estero	9,345
Tierra del Fuego, Antártida e Islas del Atlántico Sur	2,888
Tucumán	16,506

Migration

- Access to secondary and higher education
- More opportunities for employment (temporary to permanent)
- Insecurity and displacement from the territories they inhabited
- Environmental degradation
- Climate change (rising sea levels, drought, flooding, loss of glaciers)
- Networks of kin in urban and metropolitan areas (Andes and the Lowlands)

Environmental degradation and climate change

- Adaptation to a more urban, market-based lifestyle (water, sewage, solid waste, vector control)
- Adaptation to climate change, increased drought, rainfall, loss of snowfields, rising sea level

Sateré-Maués, AM, Brazil...

Policies and conventions

- ILO Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention 169 (1989/in force 1991): ratified by 24 countries/15 in LAC. (Indigenous and Tribal Populations Convention of 1957)
- IFC Performance Standard 7 (PS-7) on Indigenous Peoples (2012)
- World Bank Environmental and Social Standard 7 (ESS-7) on Indigenous Peoples/Sub-Saharan African Historically Underserved Traditional Local Communities (2016)
- UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People (2007)

ILO 169

- (1989/in force 1991): currently ratified by 24 countries (15 in LAC) updates the 1957 Indigenous and Tribal Populations Convention
- Art. 7 “shall have the right to decide their own priorities for the process of development...”
- “Governments shall take measures, in co-operation with the peoples concerned, to protect and preserve the environment of the territories they inhabit.”
- “...free and informed consent” in cases of relocation

IFC PS7

- Approved 2012, based on Indigenous Peoples 2006
- Respect for human rights, avoid and minimize impacts, and promote sustainable development benefits and opportunities
- Establish and maintain an ongoing relationship based on informed consultation and participation (ICP) with the indigenous peoples affected by a project through the project's life cycle
- Free, prior, informed consent (FPIC) – in specific circumstances
- Respect, preserve the culture, knowledge and practices of indigenous peoples

World Bank ESS 7 (2016)

- Indigenous peoples/Sub-Saharan African historically underserved traditional local communities
- FPIC in three circumstances:
 - Adverse impacts on land and/or natural resources
 - Relocation
 - Impacts on cultural heritage
- Meaningful consultation and good faith negotiation
- Must be documented, IPDPs
- Does not require unanimity

UNDRIP

- United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples
- UN Resolution approved in September 2007
- Self-determination, autonomy, indigenous institutions and the right to participate in the political, economic, social and cultural life of the state
- No relocation without FPIC
- Redress and repatriation of property taken without consent
- FPIC for legislative and administrative measures
- Rights of women, elders, youth and persons with disabilities...

UNDERSTANDING THE CONTEXT

Challenges related to ideas of territory, community and
decision-making

Land and Community

- The concept of “the community” is largely determined by legislation and historical precedent (to facilitate interaction with the state). Example of Paraguay’s Law 904/81, *Registro de Líderes*
- Application of Western concepts of land ownership and social organization to very different ideas of rights over land and resources
- Different levels of inclusion, e.g. *Tapyi* and *Tekoha. Aldeas* in the Chaco
- Settlement patterns generated through the articulation of kinship and leadership
- Tension between dispersion and association

Decision-making processes

- Who, if anyone, can legitimately represent a people?
- Religious, secular and specialist leaders
- The authority of the assembly
- Consensus and voting...
- Voices of women
- Voices of young people
- The challenge of administration

Administration of Assets

- Difficulty of defending land/territory, even when indigenous people have formal legal rights of ownership (e.g. invasions, overlapping titles, leasing in Paraguay)
- Challenge of administering funds (contradictory values, absence of rules or protocols and lack of social control)
- Generation of internal and external, often violent, conflicts
- Contradictory notions of customary law

Priorities

INTERNAL

- Consolidate local capacity:
- To defend indigenous rights to land and natural resources
- To administer land and collective resources
- To develop, manage and maintain community services and infrastructure
- To take an active role in the decision-making processes of the wider society

GOVERNMENT

- To legislate for the protection of indigenous land and resources
- To ensure indigenous peoples' access to the benefits of citizenship (especially justice)
- To enforce the rights of indigenous peoples in situations of conflict
- To proactively encourage and work with indigenous professionals

A wide-angle photograph of a rural landscape. In the foreground, a lush green cornfield is planted in neat rows. To the right, a traditional hut with a thatched roof and walls made of vertical wooden poles stands on a dirt path. Several tall, leafy trees are scattered throughout the scene, some in the background and some closer to the hut. The sky is a clear, bright blue with a few wispy white clouds. The overall atmosphere is peaceful and rural.

THANK YOU